

Supplementary Material for

DataLight: Data-Centric Offline Reinforcement Learning for Traffic Signal Control

Liang Zhang¹, Yutong Zhang², Xiaofeng Gao¹, and Chen Li³ (✉)

¹ Shanghai Jiao Tong University, Shanghai 200240, China

liangzhang96@sjtu.edu.cn, gao-xf@cs.sjtu.edu.cn

² Beijing University of Posts and Telecommunications, Beijing 100876, China

zhangyutong_2004@foxmail.com

³ The University of Osaka, Osaka 567-0047, Japan li.chen.d3c@osaka-u.ac.jp

A Implementation and Model Details

All experiments were conducted on a workstation with an AMD Ryzen 9 5900X CPU and 48GB RAM. DataLight does not require GPU acceleration in our implementation. However, the large-scale NY scenarios require sufficient memory because they involve substantially more intersections and transitions than the JN and HZ scenarios.

A.1 Relationship between delay and velocity unsaturation degree

Delay of a vehicle is defined as the time a vehicle has traveled within the environment minus the expected travel time (which equals the distance divided by the speed limit) [5]. It can be formulated as follows:

$$Delay(x) = \frac{d}{V_{ave}(x)} - \frac{d}{V_{max}}, \quad (1)$$

where d is the traveled distance, $V_{ave}(x)$ is the average velocity of vehicle x , and V_{max} is the permitted maximum velocity.

When Delay is evaluated at the one-second level, i.e. $d = V_{ave}(x) \times 1$, it becomes:

$$Delay(x) = 1 - \frac{V_{ave}(x)}{V_{max}}. \quad (2)$$

This equation is similar in form to our proposed traffic feature, velocity unsaturation degree:

$$1 - \frac{V(x)}{V_{max}} \quad (3)$$

where $V(x)$ is the instantaneous velocity at the observation time.

Despite apparent similarities, the two states exhibit significant differences, both in terms of calculation methods and their interpretive meanings. To equate the two states, stringent conditions must be met:

- The calculation of Delay must occur over a one-second interval. For example, to determine the Delay at time t , observations must be made from $t - 1$ to t , and not at any other times.

- Each vehicle must maintain a constant speed during this one-second period. This condition is challenging to fulfill due to the complex traffic environment.

In summary, although delay under certain restrictive conditions may appear formulaically similar to velocity unsaturation degree, their actual meanings and calculation procedures differ substantially. In practice, these conditions are difficult to satisfy in microscopic traffic simulation or real traffic systems, where vehicle speeds vary continuously due to car-following behavior, signal changes, and interactions with nearby vehicles.

A.2 Motivation of spatial segmentation

As vehicles move along the road, their spatial positions evolve over time, giving rise to spatiotemporal dependence. For instance, a vehicle that reaches a new spatial location after a time interval Δt introduces both spatial and temporal correlations between its previous and current positions, as illustrated in Fig. A.1(a). Therefore, as shown in Fig. A.1(b), partitioning the road into discrete spatial segments allows us to model not only the spatiotemporal correlation among adjacent segments but also long-range dependencies across non-adjacent segments. Based on the spatiotemporal characteristics of these segments, we model their features using sequential modeling techniques that account for their temporal and spatial continuity.

Fig. A.1. Illustration of (a) ordered spatiotemporal dependencies arising from vehicle movement and (b) spatial segmentation of the traffic network.

A.3 Ablation on segment number

DataLight’s performance is assessed using different state representations based on different road segmentation. For all offline datasets, actions are set with a duration of 10 seconds. The approach involves segmenting a 400-meter area approaching the intersection into either four or eight segments. The results, as depicted in Table A.1, highlight DataLight’s performance with these diverse state representations. Overall, DataLight achieves better performance with the

Table A.1. Performance with state representations using four or eight segments (ATT in seconds).

Segments	Dataset	JN dataset			HZ dataset	
		JN1	JN2	JN3	HZ1	HZ2
4	ROD	239.72 ± 0.48	225.50 ± 0.30	223.00 ± 0.32	264.48 ± 0.45	290.22 ± 8.23
	MOD	239.41 ± 0.76	226.68 ± 0.40	223.35 ± 0.31	266.25 ± 0.35	305.79 ± 2.50
	EOD	236.87 ± 0.16	223.39 ± 0.47	220.00 ± 0.51	263.08 ± 0.26	294.42 ± 7.56
8	ROD	238.69 ± 1.00	223.82 ± 0.56	221.44 ± 0.70	263.09 ± 0.37	296.64 ± 7.72
	MOD	238.87 ± 0.71	224.67 ± 0.62	222.13 ± 0.87	264.27 ± 0.53	300.76 ± 4.32
	EOD	235.05 ± 0.36	221.29 ± 0.16	218.56 ± 0.19	261.50 ± 0.14	296.76 ± 3.95

eight-segment state representation in most JN and HZ settings. Based on these findings, the eight-segmented state representation is chosen as the default for DataLight.

A.4 DataLight network details

Spatial encoding. The state inputs undergo an initial embedding layer and are then concatenated by

$$\mathbf{F}_{l,i} = \text{Emb}(s_{l,i}) \oplus \text{Emb}(s_{l,i+8}) \oplus \text{Emb}(s_{l,i+16}), \quad (4)$$

where i ranges from 0 to 7, corresponding to the 8 segments, and \oplus denotes the concatenate operation. In this context, each feature is embedded from 1-dimensional to 6-dimensional using a Multi-Layer Perceptron (MLP). A total of 24 MLPs are employed, resulting in 288 (12×24) parameters. For the concatenated features corresponding to each segment, an MLP is used to embed them from 18-dimensional to 16-dimensional. A total of 8 MLPs (corresponding to 8 segments) are used, resulting in 2432 (304×8) parameters. To model the spatial sequence features, we added a learnable position encoding layer, which consists of 128 parameters in total. Then, multi-head self-attention (MHA) [3] is employed for spatial encoding (SE).

$$\mathbf{F}_l = \text{MHA}(\mathbf{F}_{l,0} \oplus \mathbf{F}_{l,1} \oplus \cdots \oplus \mathbf{F}_{l,7}), \quad (5)$$

where a 4-head multi-head attention network is used, with a key dimension of 16, comprising a total of 4304 parameters. The current phase in the input is embedded from 1-dimensional to 6-dimensional using an MLP with 12 parameters. The embedded current phase feature is concatenated with the aforementioned features (flattened spatial features) and then embedded into a 24-dimensional space using another MLP, which contains 3240 parameters.

Feature fusion. MHA is employed to integrate features from all incoming lanes for each phase:

$$\mathbf{F}^p = \text{Mean}(\text{MHA}(\mathbf{F}_l \oplus \mathbf{F}_k)), l, k \in \mathcal{L}_p, \quad (6)$$

where p denotes each phase, \mathcal{L}_p is the set of participating entering lanes of phase p . A 4-head multi-head attention network is used four times to construct the phase feature, with a key dimension of 24, comprising a total of 9528 parameters.

Phase correlation. Fused phase feature with MHA is used to capture inter-phase correlations:

$$\mathbf{F}^{\mathcal{P}} = \text{MHA}(\mathbf{F}^A \oplus \mathbf{F}^B \oplus \mathbf{F}^C \oplus \mathbf{F}^D), \mathcal{P} = \{A, B, C, D\}. \quad (7)$$

A 4-head multi-head attention network is used, with a key dimension of 24, comprising a total of 9528 parameters.

Q-value prediction. The phase features are further processed to obtain the Q-value of each action:

$$\tilde{q} = \text{DuelingBlock}(\text{Embed}(\mathbf{F}^{\mathcal{P}})), \quad (8)$$

where DuelingBlock is the dueling module [4]. Here, a total of 6 MLPs are used, comprising 1862 ($500 + 420 \times 3 + 21 + 81$) parameters. In summary, the network of DataLight contains a total of 31,322 trainable parameters.

A.5 Offline dataset generation

Table A.2. Behavior-policy performance used for generating offline datasets (ATT in seconds; smaller is better).

Dataset	Action Duration	JN dataset			HZ dataset	
		JN1	JN2	JN3	HZ1	HZ2
ROD	10s	590.92	537.05	539.29	577.24	483.43
	15s	559.76	507.28	515.84	555.41	464.70
	20s	560.02	514.37	519.54	572.95	471.69
MOD	10s	321.36	297.76	284.39	308.15	381.81
	15s	289.06	262.40	259.93	308.16	345.31
	20s	282.29	269.97	268.85	313.74	341.57
EOD	10s	247.20	226.13	223.62	264.25	325.94
	15s	246.76	233.85	230.41	271.68	310.25
	20s	254.39	244.20	239.19	282.08	315.91
COD	10s	612.36	549.21	542.83	554.73	462.62
	15s	429.27	370.34	384.89	497.87	408.31
	20s	443.08	369.91	390.17	483.38	404.49

Offline datasets with various action durations are detailed in Table A.2. Excluding COD, each dataset comprises 100K transitions. For COD with action durations of 10s, 15s, and 20s, there are 24,480, 16,320, and 12,240 transitions, respectively.

A.6 Model performance with different offline datasets

Table A.3. DataLight performance under different offline datasets (ATT in seconds).

Dataset	Action Duration	JN dataset			HZ dataset	
		JN1	JN2	JN3	HZ1	HZ2
ROD	10s	238.69 ± 1.00	223.82 ± 0.56	221.44 ± 0.70	263.09 ± 0.37	296.64 ± 7.72
	15s	240.72 ± 0.72	229.88 ± 0.88	226.01 ± 0.50	268.75 ± 0.28	301.15 ± 5.46
	20s	250.26 ± 0.39	242.84 ± 0.48	236.69 ± 0.31	281.62 ± 0.64	296.95 ± 3.59
MOD	10s	238.87 ± 0.71	224.67 ± 0.62	222.13 ± 0.87	264.27 ± 0.53	300.76 ± 4.32
	15s	242.56 ± 0.56	231.46 ± 0.23	227.21 ± 0.34	270.73 ± 0.70	291.89 ± 3.96
	20s	250.60 ± 0.64	242.94 ± 0.37	235.46 ± 0.44	282.63 ± 0.47	296.82 ± 1.24
EOD	10s	235.05 ± 0.36	221.29 ± 0.16	218.56 ± 0.19	261.50 ± 0.14	296.76 ± 3.95
	15s	243.25 ± 0.51	231.18 ± 0.29	227.43 ± 0.35	270.71 ± 0.41	301.73 ± 5.89
	20s	248.81 ± 0.42	240.45 ± 0.34	234.95 ± 0.43	278.24 ± 0.34	303.15 ± 10.68
COD	10s	309.20 ± 4.42	239.03 ± 0.72	266.01 ± 2.75	282.07 ± 5.73	321.63 ± 2.40
	15s	270.26 ± 1.30	253.42 ± 0.82	249.26 ± 0.52	297.29 ± 0.55	315.04 ± 1.32
	20s	266.54 ± 1.10	258.45 ± 0.48	250.82 ± 0.35	300.65 ± 0.62	314.55 ± 6.34

DataLight is evaluated when trained with different offline datasets. Table A.3 demonstrates the model performance with ATT in seconds. When trained with ROD, MOD, and EOD, DataLight performs best under JN and HZ with the action duration as 10s (which is used to generate the offline datasets). When trained with COD, DataLight performs best among all the datasets with the action duration as 20s. When tested under NY, DataLight consistently performs best with the action duration as 20s.

A.7 Hyperparameter tuning for offline RL baselines

We employed an offline reinforcement learning (RL) baseline that underwent fine-tuning to achieve optimal performance. The offline RL baseline encompasses Behavior Cloning (BC), Batch-Constrained deep Q-learning (BCQ), and Conservative Q-Learning (CQL). To adapt these methods for the Traffic Signal Control (TSC) domain, they are integrated with the network architecture of AttentionLight and the state representations of Advanced-CoLight. These state representations include the current phase, traffic movement pressure, and effective running vehicle number. Additionally, pressure was utilized as the reward function.

We tested the following configurations and selected the best ones for use in the baseline. All tests employed the EOD training model and compared their control performance on JN1. The configurations tested are as follows: initially, the batch size was set to 500, and the learning rates were varied as follows: config1-1 at 0.05, config1-2 at 0.01, config1-3 at 0.001, and config1-4 at 0.0001. During this process, the weight for the CQL loss was set to 0.0001. Based on the results, we

identified the optimal learning rates: for BC and CQL, the best learning rate was 0.001, whereas for BCQ, the best learning rate was 0.01.

Table A.4. Hyperparameter tuning of BC, BCQ, and CQL on the JN1-EOD validation setting (ATT in seconds; smaller is better).

Model	config1-1	config1-2	config1-3	config1-4	config2-1	config2-2
BC	1303.73 \pm 0.00	254.47 \pm 15.93	242.74 \pm 0.63	245.23 \pm 1.70	245.61 \pm 1.98	243.95 \pm 0.89
BCQ	1303.73 \pm 0.00	247.50 \pm 0.82	251.45 \pm 1.02	255.59 \pm 1.71	752.08 \pm 25.81	250.18 \pm 1.41
CQL	1303.73 \pm 0.00	251.96 \pm 1.04	249.41 \pm 0.91	250.52 \pm 1.31	250.74 \pm 1.13	253.84 \pm 1.06

Subsequently, we conducted further experiments to determine the optimal batch size, using the following configurations, with a learning rate of 0.001 for BC and CQL, and a learning rate of 0.01 for BCQ: config2-1 with a batch size of 100, and config2-2 with a batch size of 1000. The final results are presented in Table A.4.

Table A.5. Sensitivity of CQL to the CQL loss weight on the JN1-EOD validation setting (ATT in seconds; smaller is better).

Model	config3-1	config3-2	config3-3	config3-4
CQL [2]	251.20 \pm 0.53	251.45 \pm 0.78	249.41 \pm 0.91	252.30 \pm 1.07

For CQL, we conducted further testing on the weight of the CQL loss to identify the optimal value. We used the following weight configurations: config3-1 with a weight of 0, config3-2 with a weight of 0.00001, config3-3 with a weight of 0.0001, and config3-4 with a weight of 0.001. The results are presented in Table A.5.

A.8 Analysis of decision transformer

DT [1], as another advanced offline RL method, has demonstrated strong learning performance. We evaluate the applicability of DT to TSC. The code for DT was reproduced as described in its original paper, with the returns-to-go set to -351. The model was trained on EOD and ROD datasets and tested on JN1. We used the following configurations to train the model, where K denotes the context length used by DT.

Initially, the batch size was set to 500 and the learning rate to 0.001. The configurations were as follows: config4-1: $K=1$ trained on EOD; config4-2: $K=2$ trained on EOD; config4-3: $K=1$ trained on ROD; config4-4: $K=2$ trained on ROD. In the subsequent configurations, all models were trained on ROD with $K=1$ and a batch size of 500: config5-1 with a learning rate of 0.01 and config5-2

Table A.6. Performance comparison under different configurations (ATT in seconds).

Model	config4-1	config4-2	config4-3	config4-4
DT [1]	1243.98 \pm 170.68	1237.00 \pm 195.14	690.43 \pm 19.19	1079.83 \pm 120.70
Model	config5-1	config5-2	config6-1	config6-2
DT [1]	1254.10 \pm 166.07	812.31 \pm 61.48	612.13 \pm 123.02	696.41 \pm 70.69

with a learning rate of 0.0001. Then, with a learning rate of 0.001 and $K=1$, the configurations were as follows: config6-1 with a batch size of 100 and config6-2 with a batch size of 1000. The final results are presented in Table A.6. These results show that DT does not achieve competitive performance under the tested configurations. A possible reason is that TSC trajectories differ from standard single-agent offline RL trajectories. First, signal actions are executed for relatively long durations, making the temporal resolution of decision sequences coarse. Second, the offline datasets contain transitions from multiple decentralized intersections, which can make trajectory-level return conditioning difficult without a TSC-specific tokenization scheme.

B Additional Experimental Results

This section provides additional results on COD. COD is generated by FixedTime and is used to approximate structured cyclic-control logs rather than expert demonstrations. We evaluate both single-duration COD and mixed COD to examine whether DataLight can learn from structured but potentially suboptimal behavior data.

Table B.1. Performance comparison on cyclical offline dataset (ATT in seconds).

Method	JN dataset			HZ dataset		NY dataset	
	JN1	JN2	JN3	HZ1	HZ2	NY1	NY2
BC	437.96 \pm 0.00	364.83 \pm 0.00	384.15 \pm 0.00	474.81 \pm 0.00	397.73 \pm 0.00	1458.01 \pm 0.00	1715.63 \pm 0.00
BCQ	276.03 \pm 0.47	277.32 \pm 1.04	261.38 \pm 1.09	360.81 \pm 2.25	383.83 \pm 2.89	1170.71 \pm 24.62	1542.65 \pm 6.40
CQL	274.90 \pm 0.73	271.08 \pm 0.95	260.68 \pm 0.79	332.46 \pm 3.22	356.60 \pm 2.23	1336.52 \pm 10.03	1630.91 \pm 16.90
DataLight	266.54 \pm 1.10	258.45 \pm 0.48	250.82 \pm 0.35	300.65 \pm 0.62	314.55 \pm 6.34	996.32 \pm 22.47	1335.59 \pm 48.99
Improvement	\uparrow 3.04%	\uparrow 4.66%	\uparrow 3.78%	\uparrow 9.57%	\uparrow 11.79%	\uparrow 14.90%	\uparrow 13.42%

References

- Chen, L., Lu, K., Rajeswaran, A., Lee, K., Grover, A., Laskin, M., Abbeel, P., Srinivas, A., Mordatch, I.: Decision transformer: Reinforcement learning via sequence modeling. *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems* **34**, 15084–15097 (2021)

Table B.2. DataLight performance under different evaluation action durations when trained on mixed COD (ATT in seconds; smaller is better).

Duration	JN dataset			HZ dataset		NY dataset	
	JN1	JN2	JN3	HZ1	HZ2	NY1	NY2
10s	276.81 ± 2.71	231.18 ± 0.82	237.87 ± 1.53	267.44 ± 0.41	308.05 ± 0.96	1099.72 ± 85.25	1250.17 ± 11.04
15s	255.06 ± 1.26	232.20 ± 0.49	228.77 ± 0.27	271.40 ± 0.39	296.44 ± 0.44	902.29 ± 39.97	1239.48 ± 36.17
20s	255.91 ± 1.04	243.39 ± 0.45	237.86 ± 0.73	281.41 ± 0.21	300.13 ± 0.77	970.75 ± 86.56	1280.96 ± 35.60
25s	265.97 ± 0.88	255.26 ± 0.91	248.29 ± 0.66	292.98 ± 0.40	308.06 ± 1.04	1000.79 ± 89.40	1391.65 ± 79.90

- Kumar, A., Zhou, A., Tucker, G., Levine, S.: Conservative Q-learning for offline reinforcement learning. *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems* **33**, 1179–1191 (2020)
- Vaswani, A., Shazeer, N., Parmar, N., Uszkoreit, J., Jones, L., Gomez, A.N., Kaiser, Ł., Polosukhin, I.: Attention is all you need. *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems* **30** (2017)
- Wang, Z., Schaul, T., Hessel, M., Hasselt, H., Lanctot, M., Freitas, N.: Dueling network architectures for deep reinforcement learning. In: *International Conference on Machine Learning*, pp. 1995–2003. PMLR (2016)
- Wei, H., Zheng, G., Gayah, V., Li, Z.: A survey on traffic signal control methods. *arXiv preprint arXiv:1904.08117* (2019)